

SYNTHESIS OF CORROSION INHIBITOR BASED ON MONOETHANOLAMINE AND PHOSPHATE ACID

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Abstract. In this article, the optimal conditions for synthesizing corrosion inhibitors based on monoethanolamine, phosphoric acid, and formalin. The structure of this obtained corrosion inhibitor was analyzed by IR-spectra.

Keywords: monoethanolamine, phosphoric acid, formalin, corrosion inhibitor, IR-spectrum.

Introduction

The process of corrosion is a process of chemical and electrochemical as well as biological degradation of metals as a result of environmental effects [1,2]. According to the mechanism of the process, there is chemical, electrochemical, and biochemical corrosion. Corrosion begins at the surface of the metal and spreads deeper with further development of the process. The environment in which metal corrosion occurs is various liquids and gases [3,4]. Various amines, ketones, aliphatic carboxylic acids, and amino acids, as well as products of the interaction of amino alcohols and their derivatives with sulfonamides, carboxylic acids, ethers, and aldehydes, are used as organic inhibitors [5,6]. Amino acids such as glycine, methionine, and histidine glutamic acid are used as inhibitors against steel corrosion in sulfuric acid, aspartic acid in hydrochloric acid, alanine chloride, and sulfuric acid [7,8].

Experimental part

Materials

Monoethanolamine, Phosphoric acid and Formaldehyde are used to syntheses a new corrosion inhibitor . All chemical reagents: orthophosphoric acid, monoethanolamine, and formaldehyde were purchased "chemically pure" from “Merit Chemicals” company.

Methods. The structure of this synthesized corrosion inhibitor was carried out and analyzed on a SHIMADZU (IRAffinity-1S) device. The gravimetric method was used to determine the inhibition efficiency of the synthesized inhibitor.

Synthesis of MFP-1 brand corrosion inhibitor. It was carried out in a 250 cm³ round-bottomed flask equipped with a stirrer, a reflux condenser and a thermometer. First, monoethanolamine and phosphoric acid were mixed different ratio at a temperature of 65-70 °C for 15 minutes, then formalin was added dropwise and the temperature was increased to a temperature of 95-100 °C, and the reaction was stirred for 90 minutes. Reaction product. It is 88,9 % and it is a pale yellow and dark substance, which dissolves well in hot water.

Results and Discussion

IR spectroscopy analysis. According to the results of the IR spectrum of MFP-1, groups corresponding to absorption maxima in the following range are given: 2931-2819 cm⁻¹ ν (ON), 1635-1525 cm⁻¹, ν (-CONHR), 1458 cm⁻¹ vs(-O- CH₂-), vs(-N-CH₂), 1340 cm⁻¹ vs(R=O), 1037 cm⁻¹ ν (P-O-C) (Fig. 2.1).

Figure 2.1. IR spectrum image of MFP-1 brand corrosion inhibitor

According to the analysis of the IR spectrum of MFP-1, vibrational lines of the (OH) bound hydroxyl group appeared in the 2931-2819 cm^{-1} range, valence deformation vibration lines of the secondary amide group appeared in the ν (-CONHR) range of 1635-1525 cm^{-1} , and ν s(-O-CH₂), ν s(-N-CH₂) groups in the 1458 cm^{-1} area, phosphorus oxygen bond in the 1340 cm^{-1} ν s(R=O) area, 1111 cm^{-1} bond, absorption maxima corresponding to ν (P-O-C) ether group at 1037 cm^{-1} were formed. According to the results of IR analysis, the formula of this substance can be said as follows [9].

Conclusion

In this research, the optimal conditions for the synthesis of MFP-1 brand corrosion inhibitor based on monoethanolamine, phosphoric acid, and formalin were determined. The structure of the synthesized corrosion inhibitor was analyzed using IR spectra. Also, its absorption efficiency in aqueous medium was 88,9 % when it was organized using the gravimetric method.

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